

A study of oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols by diethylammonium chlorochromate

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Abstract : Kinetics of oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols by diethylammonium chlorochromate (DEACC) has been studied in aqueous-acetic acid medium. The oxidation of various primary as well as secondary alcohols by DEACC resulted in the formation of corresponding aldehydes and ketones respectively in good yields. The reaction is first order in DEACC and Michaelis-Menten type in alcohols. The reaction is first order with respect to hydrogen ion concentration. A suitable mechanism of the reaction has also been proposed.

Keywords : Diethylammonium chlorochromate, mechanism, alcohol, oxidation.

Introduction

In continuation to our work on kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of alcohols by morpholinium chlorochromate¹ (MCC), piperidinium chlorochromate² (PipCC) and 2-picolinium chlorochromate³ (2-PicCC), we report here, the kinetics of oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols by diethylammonium chlorochromate in aqueous-acetic acid as solvent.

The oxidation of primary as well secondary alcohols resulted in the formation of corresponding aldehydes and ketones. The overall reaction may be presented as :

The reaction shows Michaelis-Menten type behaviour with respect to concentration of substrate (alcohol) (Table 1). Plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Alc}]$ gives straight line with positive intercept indicating formation of 1 : 1 complex between reagent (DEACC) and substrate (alcohol) before rate determining step. The kinetic behaviour indicates first order dependence on concentration of reagent (DEACC) and acid⁴ (Table 2). The observed rate constant of acid catalysed oxidation increases with decrease in dielectric constant of medium (Table 3) due to polar

Table 1. Effect of concentration of reactants on reaction rate at 298 K in acid media

[H ⁺] = 0.5 mol dm ⁻³ , acetic acid = 60% (v/v)			
10 ² × [Alcohol] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ × [DEACC] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ × k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	
		Ethanol	2-Butanol
1.0	2.0	4.10	1.02
2.0	2.0	5.10	2.23
3.0	2.0	5.70	2.51
4.0	2.0	6.30	2.90
5.0	2.0	6.42	3.00
6.0	2.0	6.52	3.01
5.0	3.0	7.67	4.07
5.0	4.0	7.69	4.08
5.0	5.0	7.70	4.10
5.0	6.0	7.75	4.11

Table 2. Effect of concentration of acid on reaction rate at 298 K

[Alcohol] = 0.05 mol dm ⁻³ , [DEACC] = 0.002 mol dm ⁻³ , acetic acid = 60% (v/v)		
[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ × k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	
	Ethanol	2-Butanol
0.3	4.00	1.01
0.4	5.12	1.21
0.5	6.33	2.03
0.6	7.09	2.57
0.7	8.23	2.70
0.8	10.00	2.81

Note

Table 3. Effect of concentration of solvent on reaction rate at 298 K

[Alcohol] = 0.05 mol dm⁻³, [DEACC] = 0.002 mol dm⁻³,
[H⁺] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³

Acetic acid = 60% (v/v)	Dielectric constant	10 ³ × k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	
30	72.2	0.09	1.01
40	63.3	1.01	1.14
50	56.0	2.23	1.21
60	38.5	3.82	1.32

character of transition state as compared to the reactants^{5,6}. There is no effect of base, diethyl amine, on the rate of reaction, indicating that DEACC is not hydrolysed during oxidation.

Mechanism :

The reaction proceeds by formation of ester intermediate similar to that of other known oxidising agents^{7,8}.

Table 4. k_{obs} and yield of the resulting products

[Alcohol] = 0.05 mol dm⁻³, [DEACC] = 0.002 mol dm⁻³,
acetic acid = 60% (v/v)

Sl. no.	Substrate	Product	Yield (%)	10 ³ × k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)
1.	Ethanol	CH ₃ CHO	86	6.42
2.	Methanol	HCHO	85	3.03
3.	<i>n</i> -Butanol	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇ CHO	88	7.07
4.	Iso-amyl alcohol	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉ CHO	96	12.5
5.	Benzyl alcohol	C ₆ H ₅ CHO	89	4.02
6.	2-Butanol	2-C ₃ H ₈ CO	84	3.00
7.	Iso-propyl alcohol	2-C ₂ H ₆ CO	91	12.00
8.	Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	93	7.50

(DEACC) functions as good oxidant for primary and secondary alcohols in aqueous acetic acid medium.

where R = -H for primary alcohols and -CH₃ for secondary alcohols;

R₁ = -H, -CH₃, -C₂H₅, -C₃H₇, -C₄H₉, -C₆H₅ for primary alcohols and -CH₃, -C₂H₅, -C₄H₇ for secondary alcohols

The oxidation of other alcohols by DEACC presents a similar kinetic picture, i.e. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the reductant and solvent effects and dependence on the hydrogen ions are of similar nature in all these alcohols. From the percentage yield of the products of primary and secondary alcohols (Table 4), it is clear that yield found in case of primary and secondary alcohols are high. Thus diethylammonium chlorochromate

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent quality. 2-Butanol (Sisco), cyclohexanol (Thomas-Baker) was distilled and middle fractions were collected. Methanol (absolute) was first distilled over sodium methoxide followed by refluxing for 4 h over magnesium methoxide in presence of iodine as catalyst followed by fractionation. Butanol (Qualigens), benzyl alcohol (Merck), isoamyl alco-

hol (absolute) were used as such.

Preparation of complex :

Diethylammonium chlorochromate (DEACC) was prepared by dissolving 0.05 mol (5 g) of chromium trioxide in 9.2 ml of 6 M HCl. To this solution, 0.05 mol (3.65 g) of diethyl amine was added in small proportions with stirring while keeping reaction mixture in ice bath. Yellow-orange solid so obtained was filtered and dried in the folds of filter paper. These precipitates were recrystallized from acetone and shining crystals were obtained. The elemental analysis of the compound corresponded to formula, $[(C_2H_5)_2NH_2]^+[CrO_3Cl]^-$; m.p. 98 °C; molecular formula weight 209.54 g/mol; molar conductivity, $\lambda_m = 167.15 \text{ mho cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Diethylammonium chlorochromate (DEACC) is soluble in acetone, dimethyl sulphoxide, dimethyl formamide, tetrahydro furan, acetic acid, ethyl acetate, nitrobenzene but partially soluble in chloroform. The chemical composition of DEACC was confirmed by elemental analysis (Found : Cr, 24.51; Cl, 16.69; C, 22.87; H, 5.63; N, 6.54. Calcd. : Cr, 24.81; Cl, 16.91; C, 22.91; H, 5.72; N, 6.68) and the infrared spectrum (KBr) which exhibited bands at 3438(w), 2984(w), 2846(s), 2466(w), 2371(w), 2064(w), 1629(w), 1452(s), 1390(m), 1308(w), 1224(w), 1197(w), 1159(w), 1076(w), 1046(m), 1034(m), 991(m), 975(m), 948(s), 902(s), 886(s), 781(m), 565(m), 484(s) and 437(m) cm^{-1} characteristics of various groups in DEACC.

Kinetic measurements :

The pseudo-first order conditions were attained by monitoring a large excess ($\times 10$ or more) of the alcohols over DEACC. The solvent was aqueous-acetic acid. The reactions were followed at room temperature by monitoring the decrease in [DEACC] spectrophotometrically at $\lambda = 259.6 \text{ nm}$. No other reactant or product has significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order

rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear plots of $\log [\text{DEACC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetics runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 4\%$.

Product analysis :

Product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, alcohol (0.01 mol) and DEACC (0.02 mol) were dissolved in 100 ml of the solvent (60% v/v aqueous acetic acid) and kept in the dark for 12 h to ensure completion of the reaction. A saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 M hydrochloric acid was added to above solution and then kept for 12 h in refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallized from alcohol and again weighed. The yield of DNP was 75% after recrystallization. The product was identical with an authentic sample of DNP of ethanol and 2-butanol.

References

1. H. N. Sheikh, M. Sharma, A. Hussain and B. L. Kalsotra, *Oxidation Commun.*, 2005, **28**, 887.
2. H. N. Sheikh, Madhu Sharma and B. L. Kalsotra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 913.
3. S. Mahajan, B. Singh, V. S. Jasrotia, M. Sharma, H. N. Sheikh and B. L. Kalsotra, *Oxidation Commun.*, 2008, **31**, 356.
4. V. Murugan and A. Pandurangan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 377.
5. K. Balasubramanian and V. Prathiba, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 326.
6. E. S. Amis, "Solvent Effect on Reaction Rates and Mechanism", Academic, New York, 1967.
7. G. P. Panigrahi and D. D. Mahapatro, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 579.
8. Kavita Chouhan and Pardeep K. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1434.